

Experimental Analysis of Cracks Along Bimaterial Interfaces

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ABSTRACT

Interfacial crack problems between fibers and matrix in composite materials were analyzed experimentally. The specimen geometry selected was an edge-cracked bimaterial strip, which gave rise to crack length independence of fracture parameters and mode-mixities. Preliminary analysis revealed that the potential mode-mixity range for positive normal applied displacements was from $-90^\circ < \Psi < 73^\circ$ which was wider than the previous results. A biaxial delamination tester, which was capable of controlling displacements in two perpendicular directions, was developed. In addition to the usual measurements of loads and displacements, normal crack opening displacements (NCOD) were measured near the crack front using crack opening interferometry. A hybrid procedure for extracting stress intensity factors based on the measured NCOD and complementary finite element analyses were then developed. From the series of mixed mode crack initiation experiments, it could be seen that there was a large increase in toughness with large shear components. Possible cause of the increase in toughness will be discussed by considering the effect of hydrostatic tensile stress ahead of crack tip.

INTRODUCTION

Structural reliability of composite materials can be strongly affected by the fracture toughness of interfacial crack between two constituents. The failure of interfaces is an inherently mixed mode problem, particularly when cracks are constrained to grow along the interfaces because of the mismatch of material properties across the interface. If composite materials or devices comprising two or more materials are to be designed to resist interfacial cracking then the criteria that govern initiation and growth under a range of mixed mode conditions must be established.

Since the original work of Malyshev and Salganik [1], a number of studies of mixed mode effects on interfacial toughness have been conducted by Trantina [2], Anderson et. al. [3], Mulville et. al. [4], Liechti and Hanson [5], Cao and Evans [6], Wang and Suo [7], Liechti and Chai [8,9], and many others. All the studies observed that the overall interfacial toughness increased as the shear component of the fracture mode was increased.

The purpose of this work is to develop a method for providing mode I and II so that interfacial fracture could be examined over a wide range of mode-mixes. A combined experimental and

numerical method was used to elucidate interfacial debonding mechanism. The approach for obtaining a wide range of mode-mixes was to use a single specimen geometry in conjunction with a biaxial loading device. The specimen geometry selected was an edge-cracked bimaterial strip, which shows wide range of mode-mixes. A development of biaxial delamination tester, which was capable of controlling displacements in two perpendicular directions, and the measurement of normal crack opening displacements (NCOD) by crack opening interferometry are described. The results of series of crack initiation experiments over a wide range of mode-mixes are then presented. Various sources of the measured toughening effect under shear loads will be considered and discussed.

SPECIMEN GEOMETRY

Just ahead of the interfacial crack-tip at a distance r along $\theta = 0$, the stresses are given by

$$\sigma_{22} + i\sigma_{12} = \frac{K r^{i\epsilon}}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \quad (1)$$

where K is the complex stress intensity factor which is defined as $K = K_1 + iK_2$ and the bimaterial constant, ϵ , is

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{2\pi} \ln \left[\frac{\kappa_1 \mu_2 + \mu_1}{\kappa_2 \mu_1 + \mu_2} \right] \quad (2)$$

where μ is the shear modulus and κ is defined as $3 - 4\nu$ in plane strain and $(3 - \nu)/(1 + \nu)$ in plane stress. The subscript 1 and 2 refer to the upper and lower materials, respectively. The mode-mix or mixity, Ψ , was defined to be as

$$\Psi = \tan^{-1} \frac{\text{Im}[K \hat{r}^{i\epsilon}]}{\text{Re}[K \hat{r}^{i\epsilon}]} \quad (3)$$

where \hat{r} was taken $1 \mu m$ suggested by Rice [10]. Energy release rate for plane strain can be obtained from the complex stress intensity factors through

$$G = \frac{1}{4 \cosh^2 \pi \epsilon} \left[\frac{1 - \nu_1}{\mu_1} + \frac{1 - \nu_2}{\mu_2} \right] (K_1^2 + K_2^2) \quad (4)$$

A single specimen under biaxial loading was used in this work because the range of mode-mixes that could be obtained was much wider and variation in the degree of adhesion were likely to be lower. The specimen geometry and loading that was adopted was the edge-cracked bimaterial strip shown in Fig. 1 which is made up of a epoxy and glass combination. It is clamped along the boundaries at $y = \pm h_i$ ($i = 1, 2$) and can be subjected to various combinations of normal and tangential displacements.

The strip geometry is well known for its linear compliance vs. crack length relation for sufficiently long cracks. Bimaterial strip specimen shown in Fig. 1 under applied normal displacement, v_0 , has been made by Atkinson [11] who found that the energy release rate was given by

$$G = \frac{(\lambda_1 + 2\mu_1)(\lambda_2 + 2\mu_2)}{2h_1h_2} \left[\frac{\lambda_1 + 2\mu_1}{h_1} + \frac{\lambda_2 + 2\mu_2}{h_2} \right]^{-1} v_0^2 \quad (5)$$

where λ_i is one of the Lamé constants. Under applied displacement in shear direction, u_0 , energy arguments for sufficiently long cracks leads to

$$G = \frac{\mu_1\mu_2}{2h_1h_2} \left[\frac{\mu_1}{h_1} + \frac{\mu_2}{h_2} \right]^{-1} u_0^2 \quad (6)$$

The crack length is not involved in Eqs. (5) and (6), which satisfies the requirement of crack length independence of energy release rate.

$L = 150.0 \text{ (mm)}$ $h_1 = h_2 = 10.0 \text{ (mm)}$

Figure 1. The Edge Cracked Bimaterial Strip Specimen

Expected values of total energy release rate are compared with the results of finite element analysis of the specimens. However, a more important contribution of the finite element analysis is the extraction of the mode-mixities associated with particular combinations of materials of the specimens. The identification of mode-mixities in delamination of laminated composites is based on the stress intensity factors in Eq. (3). Among the various methods of extracting mixed mode interfacial fracture parameters, the conservation integral approach by Yau and Wang [12] was found to be most satisfactory and was incorporated in this study as a post processing routine in the finite element code. The auxiliary solutions required for the conservation integral technique were taken from the near tip singular solution. The materials for analysis are assumed epoxy and glass which have the values of the parameters listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Material Properties

Material	Young's Modulus E (GPa)	Poisson's ratio ν
Epoxy	1.72	0.40
Glass	68.95	0.20
Bimaterial constant $\epsilon = 0.048647$		

The invariance of total energy release rates and mode-mixities for edge cracked strip specimen over the range of crack lengths is established in Table 2 for the cases of unit amount of applied displacements normal and shear to the interface. When the analytical energy release rate solutions of Eqs. (5) and (6) were compared with those obtained from finite element analysis, the difference was less than 0.2 %.

The range of mode-mixities that can be obtained for $v_0 > 0$ are shown in Fig. 2. Pure applied normal displacements ($u_0 = 0$) give rise to a mixity of -8° , bringing out the mismatch of the elastic properties across the interface. A 1:1 ratio of shear to normal displacements is required

to produce, $\Psi = -31^\circ$ whereas a -15:1 ratio gives rise to $\Psi = 73^\circ$. The mode-mixity does not drop much below -90° for $u_o/v_o > 15$. Thus, for positively applied normal displacements, the range of mode-mixities is essentially $-90^\circ < \Psi < 73^\circ$ which covers both positive and negative shear. In the work by Cao and Evans [6], the mode mix range was $0^\circ < \Psi < 90^\circ$ by considering a number of different specimen geometries. Thus the edge-cracked bimaterial strip under biaxial loading provides a much wider and continuous range of mode-mixities for both positive and negative Ψ .

Table 2. Fracture Parameters Under Normal and Tangential Displacements

$u_o (\mu m)$	$v_o (\mu m)$	Ψ (deg)	$G_{numerical} (J/m^2)$	$G_{analytical} (J/m^2)$
0	1	-8.152	0.1757	0.1762
1	0	81.714	0.0301	0.0301

Figure 2. The Range of Mode-Mixity Under Positive Normal Displacements

EXPERIMENTS

From the preceding analysis it is clear that the development of a special loading device was required. The relatively low toughness of epoxy-glass interfaces led to the additional requirement that the applied displacements should be controlled with high resolution. Furthermore, it was important to minimize any interaction between two loading directions. The stiffness of the loading device had to be high enough that the crack initiation process (slow extension) and steady growth could be examined. Finally, the desire to measure normal crack opening displacement (NCOD) in order to examine inelastic, three-dimensional and/or contact effects in the crack tip region meant that microscope access be provided.

A schematic of the biaxial delamination tester is shown in Fig. 3. The specimen was glued along the edges to two sets of grip plates which were connected to a linear bearing and actuators. The stepper motors, ball screws, linear motion guides and optical encoders were used in a computer controlled feedback loop to provide independent displacement control to a resolution of $0.5 \mu m$.

In order to examine near-tip asymptotics, crack face contact and three-dimensional effects, it was necessary to make measurements in the crack front region in addition to global measurements. Crack opening interferometry which can measure NCOD directly was employed in this study and was shown in Fig. 4. A 45° mirror was mounted in one of the grips to

introduce a laser light through the glass for reflection by the crack faces. The reflected beams interfere and the resulting fringe patterns were caught by a microscope. For the normal incidence, a dark fringe of order m is a contour of NCOD, Δv , given by

$$\Delta v = m \frac{\lambda}{2} \quad (7)$$

Figure 3. Biaxial Delamination Tester

The wavelength λ was 632.8 nm for He-Ne laser, yielding a resolution per half fringe (bright to dark) of 158.2 nm. The fringe patterns were recorded through a video camera and timer onto a high resolution video cassette recorder. The recordings were later analyzed using a digital image analyzer system to obtain light intensity profiles along the center of the specimen. The intensity profiles were then filtered prior to thresholding in order to determine fringe locations. The whole procedure and fringe counting scheme were automated so that NCOD profiles could be obtained. The video timer allowed the NCOD measurements to be synchronized with those of the applied displacements and reactions.

Figure 4. Crack Opening Interferometry

A series of experiments applying normal loadings and sequential loadings were conducted for analyzing the interfacial crack initiation process. In the sequential loading cases, various levels of positive or negative tangential displacements were followed by normal displacements until

steady crack propagation occurred. This series of experiments allowed the fracture toughness of interface to be obtained over a wide range of mode-mixes. A series of video frames under sequential loadings is shown in Fig. 5 to illustrate crack closure/opening and propagation. The first frame, taken at a slight preload, indicated some initial opening. In the second frame, which corresponds to the maximum level of tangential displacements, the fringe density decreased (indicating decreasing NCOD) under positive shear loading. Crack initiation by normal loading occurred in frame 3, and the last frame was taken during steady crack growth.

Figure 5. Typical Fringe Patterns Under a Sequential Loading

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A series of experiments applying normal loadings and sequential loadings were conducted. A sequence of NCOD profiles was taken from the center of a series of interference patterns, corresponding to the center of a specimen, far removed from any edge effect. The measured NCOD, by themselves, do not provide sufficient information with which to extract mixed mode fracture parameters, particularly during crack initiation. A hybrid experimental/finite element analysis procedure was implemented. The procedure consists of matching the measured NCOD and finite element solutions in a near tip region and then using the matched finite element solutions to extract mixed mode fracture parameters.

The measured and predicted NCOD close to crack front when normal displacements were applied until crack initiation are compared in Fig. 6. The measurements are the discrete points and the lines are finite element solutions at corresponding levels. There was always some initial opening due to a slight preload applied to the specimen and the same preload was applied in the finite element analysis. It can be seen that close agreement was obtained at until crack initiation and that a linear analysis was sufficient.

The results of sequential loading case, which consists of positive tangential displacement followed by normal displacements are now shown in Fig. 7. The measured initial state was matched by applying fictitious amounts of normal applied displacements in the finite element analysis. As the tangential displacement were increased, the crack faces near the crack front started to close from initially open configuration until the maximum value of tangential displacement was applied. The results of sequential loading case, involving negative tangential displacement followed by normal displacements are shown in Fig. 8. As the tangential displacement were increased in a negative sense, the NCOD increased as is indicated by the results at the maximum value of tangential displacement. The results of two series of sequential loading cases stated above showed that the agreement between predictions and measurements was reasonable.

Figure 6. Comparison of NCOD Profiles Under Normal Displacement

Figure 7. NCOD Profiles Under Sequential Loading - Positive Tangential Displacement

Figure 8. NCOD Profiles Under Sequential Loading - Negative Tangential Displacement

The experiments that were analyzed were part of a series of experiments that was conducted over a range of mode-mixes from $-90^\circ < \Psi < 73^\circ$. The range was provided by applying various levels of tangential displacements followed by normal displacements until crack propagation occurred. The G_c values, interfacial fracture toughness, which were extracted from conservation integral technique [12] and Eq. (4) were collected from each experiment. The interfacial fracture toughness was plotted as a function of mode-mix, Ψ , in Fig. 9. The results were obtained from four specimens with some overlap in mode-mixity from specimen to specimen. It could be seen that there was a large increase in interfacial toughness with shear components as has been noted by a number of investigators. Another interesting feature of the results is that the degree of shielding provided by positive and negative in-plane shear is asymmetric.

Figure 9. Variation of Interfacial Toughness with Mode- Mix

CONCLUSIONS

A mixed mode delamination tester has been developed that is capable of applying a large range of mixed mode conditions for interfacial cracks. Crack initiation experiments were conducted using edge cracked epoxy-glass strip specimen for mixities from $-90^\circ < \Psi < 73^\circ$. Measured values of NCOD were compared with finite element analyses. From the series of mixed mode crack initiation experiments, it could be seen that there was a large increase in toughness with larger mode II components.

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DAMAGE
